

A Redox Titrimetric Method for the Determination of Thallium(III)

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Manuscript received 13 December 1977, accepted 24 April 1978

Thallium(III) can be quantitatively reduced to thallium(I) using excess of iron(II) at room temperature which requires about half an hour. The time factor can be reduced either by boiling or by using a complexing agent like phosphoric acid. The excess unreacted iron(II) can be titrated either with cerium(IV) sulphate using ferroin as indicator or potassium dichromate using diphenyl amine as indicator.

IRON(II) is one of the versatile reductants known. Arthur John Berry¹ has recommended a procedure for the estimation of thallium(III) in which excess of iron(II) was added to thallium(III) in dilute sulphuric acid medium, heated to boiling, cooled and titrated against standard potassium dichromate using potassium ferricyanide as an external indicator. He has observed that his method gives lower values (about 1.7%) when compared with the values obtained gravimetrically by the iodide method.

The kinetics of the reaction between thallium(III) and iron(II) in sulphuric and perchloric acid media were followed by Johnson Jr² and Forchheimer et al³ respectively.

Johnson (Jr.) preferred to use 6F sulphuric acid medium for the reduction of thallium(III) at room temperature with excess of iron(II) and the subsequent titration of the excess unreacted iron(II) after the reduction is complete, either with cerium(IV) sulphate or with standard potassium dichromate. The redox potential of thallium(III)-thallium(I) system in sulphuric acid medium is sufficiently high (1.2 V) for a satisfactory redox titrimetric titration of thallium(III) with iron(II) to be carried out. But details of the procedure to be adopted for the estimation and the error involved in the method are not available in these references. In view of the results obtained by determining the formal redox potentials of thallium(III)-thallium(I) system in various acids⁴ the details of the redox titrimetric method for the determination thallium(III) with iron(II) are now worked out by the present authors.

Direct titration of thallium(III) with iron(II) was reported⁵ from the same school. As this method needs very high concentration of phosphoric acid (more than 11M) a much cheaper method though indirect is developed now.

Experimental

Reagents : Thallium(I) and thallium(III) solutions are prepared from thallos carbonate (B.D.H. sample) and standardized as described earlier⁶. Other reagents used are of analytical reagent grade.

To obtain satisfactory results in the estimation of thallium(III) by indirect method the following conditions must be satisfied.

- (1) Thallium(I) formed in the reaction should not interfere in the subsequent titration of the excess of iron(II) with the standard oxidant.
- (2) The reaction between thallium(III) and iron(II) should be sufficiently rapid.
- (3) The reaction must be stoichiometrically completed even with a little excess of the reductant.

Effect of Thallium(I)

The interference of thallium(I) in the titration of iron(II) with cerium(IV) sulphate is studied by adding increasing quantities of thallium(I) to iron(II) solutions in 0.5M sulphuric acid medium and titrating with cerium(IV) sulphate. Typical results obtained by the authors are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF THALLIUM(I) IN THE TITRATION OF IRON(II) WITH CERIUM(IV) SULPHATE IN .5M SULPHURIC ACID MEDIUM

Iron(II) taken millimole	Thallium(I) added millimole	Iron(II) found millimole	Percentage error
0.50	0	0.5000	nil
0.50	0.05	0.4996	-0.08
0.50	0.10	0.4998	-0.04
0.50	0.20	0.5002	+0.04
0.50	0.30	0.5000	nil
0.50	0.50	0.5004	+0.08

The results in Table 1 show that thallium(I) does not interfere in the titration of iron(II) in 0.5M sulphuric acid medium. However, thallium(I) is found to interfere in the titration if the titration is carried out in hydrochloric acid medium. Also the reduction of thallium(III) by iron(II) is affected in the presence of hydrochloric acid. These facts could be easily understood, if one considers the effect of chloride ion on the formal redox potentials of the thallium system⁴. Hence chloride ion is to be avoided for these determinations.

Rapidity and Stoichiometry of the Reaction

The second and third requirements are checked by following the absorption due to ferric iron (followed spectrophotometrically), one of the products of the reaction. The results of such experiments have shown that the reaction is not sufficiently fast in a medium of 0.5M sulphuric acid. Hence the excess iron(II) is titrated, with cerium(IV) sulphate using ferroin as indicator, at various intervals of time and the results obtained are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TIME ON THE REACTION BETWEEN THALLIUM(III) AND IRON(II)

Time in minutes	Thallium(III) taken millimole	Iron(II) added millimole	Excess of Iron(II) millimole	Thallium(III) computed millimole	% error
0	0.20	0.50	0.4920	0.0040	-98
2	0.20	0.50	0.4800	0.0100	-95
5	0.20	0.50	0.4200	0.0400	-80
10	0.20	0.50	0.3160	0.0920	-54
15	0.20	0.50	0.1400	0.1800	-10
20	0.20	0.50	0.1040	0.1980	-1.0
25	0.20	0.50	0.1016	0.1992	-0.4
30	0.20	0.50	0.1000	0.2000	nil
45	0.20	0.50	0.1008	0.1996	-0.2
60	0.20	0.50	0.0992	0.2004	+0.2

The results in Table 2 show that the reaction is complete only in about 30 minutes at room temperature in 0.5M sulphuric acid medium when double the amount of iron(II), required for the stoichiometric reduction of thallium(III) is present. It is also clear from the table that iron(II) need not be added too much in excess. Double the quantity required by the stoichiometry of the reaction is enough. Hence titrimetric determination of thallium(III) is attempted.

Indirect Determination of Thallium(III) after Reduction with Iron(II) at Room Temperature

Ten ml of 0.05M iron(II) sulphate in 0.5M sulphuric acid is added to an aliquot of thallium(III) in 0.5M sulphuric acid to which about 30 ml of 0.5M sulphuric acid is added and allowed to stand for about half an hour. Then the excess iron(II) is back titrated with standard cerium(IV) sulphate solution using ferroin as indicator. Thallium(III) is calculated from the amount of unreacted excess

iron(II). Typical results of such determination are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—INDIRECT DETERMINATION OF THALLIUM(III) AFTER REDUCTION WITH IRON(II) AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Thallium(III) taken millimole	Iron(II) added millimole	Excess of Iron(II) millimole	Thallium(III) computed millimole	% error
0.0480	0.5000	0.4044	0.0478	-0.4
0.0960	0.5000	0.3080	0.0960	nil
0.1440	0.5000	0.2116	0.1442	+0.15
0.1920	0.7000	0.3164	0.1918	-0.1
0.2400	0.7000	0.2188	0.2406	+0.25

The results in Table 3 show that thallium(III) can be determined indirectly by titration with either cerium(IV) sulphate or potassium dichromate by reducing thallium(III) with excess of iron(II). But the procedure requires lot of time (about 30 minutes) for the completion of the reaction. Hence it is attempted to reduce the time factor.

Indirect Determination of Thallium(III) after Reduction with Iron(II) at Boiling Temperature

Ten ml of 0.05M iron(II) in 0.5M sulphuric acid is added to an aliquot of thallium(III) in 0.5M sulphuric acid medium to which about 30 ml of 0.5M sulphuric acid is added. Then the mixture is heated just to boiling and cooled to room temperature (since the indicator used, ferroin, is unstable at higher temperatures) and then the unreacted excess iron(II) is titrated with standard cerium(IV) sulphate. Typical results of such experiments are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF THALLIUM(III) AFTER REDUCTION WITH IRON(II) AT BOILING TEMPERATURE

Thallium(III) taken millimole	Iron(II) added millimole	Excess of Iron(II) millimole	Thallium(III) computed millimole	% error
0.2840	1.0000	0.4290	0.2855	+0.5
0.3550	1.0000	0.2852	0.3574	+0.7
0.4260	1.0000	0.1506	0.4247	-0.3
0.4970	1.5000	0.5000	0.5000	+0.6
0.5680	1.5000	0.3596	0.5702	+0.4
0.6390	1.5000	0.2132	0.6434	+0.7
0.7100	2.0000	0.5848	0.7076	-0.3
0.7810	2.0000	0.4272	0.7864	+0.7
0.8520	2.0000	0.2880	0.8560	+0.5

From the results in Table 4 it is evident that in most of the cases higher values are obtained. This is obviously due to atmospheric oxidation of iron(II) itself at higher temperature. In this connection it may be noted that Arthur John Berry¹ has recommended boiling in this method. From the results of the present authors shown in Table 4, it is clear that the method is inaccurate due to atmospheric oxidation. Hence the method needs the use of inert atmosphere for these determinations.

Though the former method gives accurate results it requires about half an hour for the reac-

TABLE 5—CATALYTIC EFFECT OF PHOSPHORIC ACID ON THE REACTION BETWEEN THALLIUM(III) AND IRON(II) AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Time in minutes	Conc. of H_3PO_4 M	Thallium(III) taken millimole	Iron(II) added millimole	Excess of Iron(II) millimole	Thallium(III) computed millimole	% error
0	0	0	0.5000	0.5000	—	—
0	0.25	0	0.5000	0.5000	—	—
0	0	0.1400	0.5000	0.4900	0.0050	*
0	0.25	0.1400	0.5000	0.2300	0.1350	-3.8
1	0.25	0.1400	0.5000	0.2212	0.1394	-0.4
2	0.25	0.1400	0.5000	0.2194	0.1403	+0.2
3	0.25	0.1400	0.5000	0.2200	0.1400	nil
4	0.25	0.1400	0.5000	0.2208	0.1396	-0.3
5	0.25	0.1400	0.5000	0.2206	0.1397	-0.2
10	0.25	0.1400	0.5000	0.2200	0.1400	nil

* Almost no reaction.

tion to be completed between thallium(III) and iron(II) (especially when iron(II) is not too much in excess when compared with thallium(III) and the later method is inaccurate because of atmospheric oxidation. In view of these observations the present authors have attempted to use a catalyst which can make the reaction much faster. This can be achieved either by complexing iron(III) or thallium(I), one of the products of the present reaction. It is an established fact that phosphate ion is one of the complexing agents of iron(III)⁷. Moreover the formal redox potential⁸ of thallium(III)-thallium(I) system in about 0.25M phosphoric acid will not be affected much when compared with its potential in sulphuric acid medium⁸ alone. Hence phosphoric acid is chosen as a complexing agent for catalysing the reaction.

Indirect Determination of Thallium(III) after Reduction with Iron(II) in the Presence of Phosphoric acid as Catalyst at Room Temperature

Excess of iron(II) is added to thallium(III) to which sufficient amount of phosphoric acid is added, given some time and the excess unreacted iron(II) is titrated against standard cerium(IV) sulphate using ferroin as indicator (or potassium dichromate using diphenyl amine as indicator). The results of such experiments (Table 5) have shown that about 2.0 ml of syrupy phosphoric acid is sufficient for every 100 ml of the reaction mixture. From the table it is also clear that the reduction of thallium(III) with excess of iron(II) under such conditions is complete within a minute at room temperature.

Utilising the above conditions different amounts of thallium(III) are determined using both the oxidants (cerium(IV) sulphate and potassium dichromate) to titrate the excess unreacted iron(II). Typical results are given in Table 6.

TABLE 6—INDIRECT DETERMINATION OF THALLIUM(III) AFTER REDUCTION WITH IRON(II) IN THE PRESENCE OF PHOSPHORIC ACID AS CATALYST AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Thallium(III) taken millimole	Iron(II) added millimole	Excess of Iron(II) millimole	Thallium(III) computed millimole	% error
Oxidant used—Ce(IV); Indicator used—Ferroin.				
0	0.4620	0.4620	—	—
0.0500	0.4620	0.3624	0.0498	-0.4
0.0750	0.4620	0.3124	0.0748	-0.3
0.1000	0.4620	0.2626	0.0970	-0.3
0.1250	0.4620	0.2116	0.1252	+0.2
0.1500	0.4620	0.1612	0.1504	+0.3
0.2000	0.6930	0.2950	0.1994	-0.3
0.2500	0.6930	0.1910	0.2510	+0.4
0.3750	0.9240	0.1760	0.3740	-0.3
0.5000	1.3860	0.3880	0.4990	-0.3
Oxidant used—Cr(VI); Indicator used—Diphenyl amine.				
0	0.4620	0.4620	—	—
0.0250	0.4620	0.4122	0.0249	-0.4
0.0500	0.4620	0.3622	0.0498	-0.2
0.0750	0.4620	0.3116	0.0752	+0.3
0.1000	0.4620	0.2626	0.0999	-0.1
0.1250	0.4620	0.2112	0.1254	+0.3

From the results in Table 6, thallium(III) can be determined within $\pm 0.4\%$ error using either cerium(IV) or chromium(VI) as oxidant. It needs neither inert atmosphere nor waiting for the completion of the reaction.

Acknowledgement

The authors' grateful thanks are due to Prof. S. R. Sagi, Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair, for his valuable suggestions.

One of the authors (G.S.P.R.) is grateful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

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